

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 30/12/2015 – 04/12/2015

Maximus Byamukama

Mary Nsabagwa

Emmanuel Kondela

Plans:

- Literature review on Proposal
- Troubleshooting 10 m Node
- Prepare Presentations for Annual meeting
- Work on Version 5 of the evaluation Report

Activities:

- Replaced the 10m Node with another mote and removed all sensors to monitor power Voltage levels
- Proposal writing
- Preparation of presentations and report for annual meeting
- Risk analysis of Second-generation prototype plans and incorporating feedback into Version 5 of the evaluation report.

Plans for next week

- Attend Annual WIMEA-ICT meeting